

Teaching innovation: comparison between project-based and traditional learning approaches

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Abstract

Innovation is a multi-faceted thematic. It ranges from economy to engineering, from management to technology development, from knowledge management to manufacture. Besides, innovation involves changing mindset and a multitude of cultural issues which can hinder its progress. Concurrently, engineering courses face a reality in which there is no specific discipline of innovation in their syllabus. According to the new technologies, the Brazilian government has started a national effort to update the engineering curriculum and challenges engineers will deal with in their professional practices. This paper presents the experience of the discipline "Innovation of Production Systems" at the University of Brasília. From 2013 to 2020, the discipline has experienced variations with different theoretical content levels, problem-based learning assignments, or contextual-based discussions concerning the markets and innovation ambients in Brazil and abroad. By analyzing the evolution of discipline content, the amount of problem-based learning demanded, the final grades, and qualitative results, we reflect on teaching innovation and having significant results beyond the own academic grades. Two hundred twelve students demonstrate that practical assignments arouse more interest from students, but the impact was irrelevant. Results suggest that the workload of innovation in engineering undergraduate courses needs to be improved from an entrepreneurial perspective.

Keywords: Innovation; Problem-based learning; Engineering Education; Entrepreneurship.

1 Introduction

Given the current dynamics of the economy, companies have invested in their innovative capacity. Companies have sought new engineers with training about the innovation process and have invested in incorporating graduates with this profile in the daily business. Among the models with greater market penetration stand out for their apparent ease of understanding, the Innovation Funnel proposed by Wheelwright and Clark (1992) and the stage-gate model[©] proposed by Cooper (2011). These and other innovation models such as lean startup or disruptive innovation need to be taught to engineering students.

According to Resolution No. 1/2019 of the Higher Education Chamber/National Council of Education CNE/CES (Brasil, 2019), the industry sector finds it is difficult to recruit skilled people to work on the frontier of knowledge. Professionals with leadership skills, teamwork, strategic planning, and management skills, the so-called soft skills. Moreover, engineers must deal with entrepreneurship concepts in a positive way (ABENGE, 2018).

It is noteworthy that teaching approaches based on lectures remain dominant in engineering education, leaving graduates poorly prepared to understand the complexities of the engineering profession (ASEE, 2009) and entrepreneur endeavors. Borrego et al. (2014) mention several studies that demonstrate the advantages of the results achieved by students using active methodologies. According to Ríos et al. (2010), under an active learning framework, the student leaves the passive role of just receiving the knowledge to take an active role in learning. According to Downing (2001), professional skills are increasingly valued, i.e., companies value skills beyond technical knowledge and specialization. According to Borrego et al. (2014), a multiple set of experiences demonstrate the effectiveness of the PBL approach to teach soft skills in many engineering areas. However, few studies present comparisons of traditional and PBL practices in one specific discipline.

According to Barbalho et al. (2017), the University of Brasília is developing its industrial engineering program, a set of active learning experiences. Some evaluation efforts have been made by researchers, approaching content apprehension (Reis et al., 2018) and general satisfaction (Zindel et al., 2012). In this context, this paper

aims to present the results of their experience in one specific course, termed Production System Innovation (ISP). This course is taught as a non-mandatory discipline, and project-based teaching varied over the semesters. There was the exclusive use of an approach based on exhibition classes and exams. We intend to explore this variation and its impact on students' grades.

In the next section, our theoretical basis is presented, and after the research methodology. Section four presents the case study. In the end, the main discussions and remarks are highlighted.

2 Innovation

The theme of innovation has been widespread in recent years, but its initial conceptualization dates back to the beginning of the last century. According to Schumpeter (1982), modern society is based on economic transformations of an evolutionary character. Its operation is driven by new methods of production, transport, new markets, and new forms of industrial organization. This condition revolutionizes the economic structure from the inside out, destroying the old and creating the new, which characterizes innovation.

Also, according to Schumpeter (op. cit.), innovation is possible due to the role of the innovative entrepreneur. Its function would be to change the production pattern, using a new idea to produce a new product, or produce it differently—Dyer et al. (2012) detail the characteristics of the innovative entrepreneur. The authors interviewed inventors of revolutionary products and services, founders and managers of companies considered innovative and realized that some skills were detained in their work process.

Christensen (2012) calls the innovator's dilemma that rational decision-making – based on execution skills – implies the difficulty many leading companies have had to maintain a hegemonic competitive position. These companies have faced breakthrough innovations, whose logic of competition differs significantly from the technological environment before them since such innovations give rise to and continue through the constitution of new value networks in unprofitable niches for established companies. These networks are driven to the most profitable environments as the advancement of rupture technologies consolidates technically and operationally.

To manage innovation, Wheelwright and Clark (1992) developed the idea of an innovation funnel. The "funnel" is a graphic representation that exemplifies the innovation process. At the funnel, entrance is the proposals for innovation, which are ideas of products to be evaluated. At the end of the funnel, we have products and services that have been selected and will be launched on the market. Throughout the funnel, the applicable market conditions and technology are considered for decision-making of the feasibility of each product and due selection, which will remain in the development process. The authors warn that one of the main difficulties of innovation is the structuring of a process that allows capturing many ideas, but that over time is frozen or finished projects that do not meet the criteria of success of the company.

The procedural aspect of innovation has been the focus of several studies. It has been consolidated in the format of works such as Barbalho and Rozenfeld (2013), which inserts several concepts of process management and knowledge of areas related to product and factory engineering. Commonly, these models present stage-gate structure©, as proposed by the seminal works of Clausing (1994) and Pugh (1990). However, it is important to mention that the development funnel is usually referred to as the stages of the innovation process that the literature has agreed to call fuzzy front end (FFE). The FEE is an allusion to the fact that the initial stage of the innovation process is the locus of the most creative activities, the proposition of the new business, new products, and services with the promotion of divergent thinking (KOEN, 2005).

3 Problem-Based Learning

The Methodology of Problem-Based Learning (PBL) proved to learn from the practice of doing, valuing, questioning, and contextualizing the ability of students to think gradually to acquire relative knowledge to solve real situations in the area of studies (Caldeira et al., 2017). Thus, it is observed that the PBL is associated

with constructivist theories, which aim to allow students to conduct their learning through research and work collaboratively to research and create projects that reflect their knowledge (Bell, 2010).

According to Krajcik & Blumenfeld (2000), meaningful learning occurs when the learner actively builds his understanding based on his experience and interaction with the world. Thus, it can be based on the perspective that the learning development, from basic to graduate education, can be subsidized by a continuous process that will require the student to have a constant reconstruction every time he can acquire and abstract new experiences (Luz et al., 2019).

The learning environment conducted through active methodologies creates cognitive learning through their actions (Hmello-Silver et al. 2006). For Balve & Albert (2015), the PBL's approach increases individual motivation and presents students with a real demand that needs to be met.

There are several studies on the use of the PBL approach. This learning methodology, covering the construction of technical and transversal skills, requires applying skills that can be characterized as "How to do"; that is, it is necessary to apply knowledge in practical contexts (Soares et al., 2013).

Previous research at the University of Brasília has analyzed the production planning and control discipline (Barbalho et al., 2017). It points to good knowledge conversion throughout the projects (Reis et al., 2018), focusing on soft skills, such as negotiation and teamwork. Luz et al. (2021) also identify teamwork as an important ability in the industrial engineering discipline of new product development at the University of Brasília. The authors also suggest that these experiences deliver better leadership skills and a stronger attitude regarding curiosity and interest in technical contents. However, this previous research didn't detect content apprehension along with the training process of soft skills. The present work is an evaluation of the innovation discipline of the Industrial Engineering syllabus.

4 Methodology

This research utilizes a case study approach (Yin, 2001). A deeper analysis is performed regarding an object of investigation, an Innovation course flexibly structured in the PBL or traditional approach. Qualitative and quantitative data was gathered, the latter employing grading datasheets and the former by registering the reflections of the course's Professor.

The grading datasheets stored data from the first semester of 2013 until the first semester of 2020, totaling 212 students, generating a specific datasheet each semester. These were analyzed and formatted, consolidated into a single document containing all individual and group activities and their respective grade summaries. A binary classification was considered for each activity used in the students' evaluation, namely "1" when the activity composed the evaluation datasheet or "0" when it was not. Statistical analysis was then conducted regarding the contents and grades for every student, and it is presented here.

5 Case Study

5.1 The Production System Innovation discipline

Figure 1 presents the main elements to characterize the Production System Innovation discipline here analyzed.

The course is part of the Department of Industrial Engineering belonging to the Faculty of Technology of the University of Brasília, located in Brasília, capital of Brazil. It is an optional course - not mandatory - that students from different faculties can take, and over the years 2012 to 2020, it was taught by the same teacher. The workload of this innovation course is four credits, which is translated into 60 hours, and it does not have other courses as a prerequisite, allowing students from different areas to have access to this important theme.

Covering the most relevant points of the subject relies on the possibility of student diversity. The objectives sought throughout the activities performed in the course are: to identify the elements of production systems for the production system project; to position the processes of innovation and product development within the production system project; to discuss the basic concepts of innovation and product development; to

discuss the concepts of sustaining innovation and disruptive innovation; to discuss the concepts of innovator DNA and to apply concepts of innovation project and product development in the context of a fictitious production system.

UNIVERSIDADE DE BRASÍLIA			
Course syllabus			
PLANO DE ENSINO DE DISCIPLINA			
FACULDADE DE TECNOLOGIA			
NÚCLEO DE ENGENHARIA DE PRODUÇÃO			
CURSO: Engenharia de Produção			
DOCENTE RESPONSÁVEL: Sanderson Barbalho			
DISCIPLINA	SEMESTRE	Créditos	PRÉ-REQUISITOS
Inovação e Sistemas de Produção	Optativa	4	60 h
OBJETIVOS:			
a) Identificar os elementos dos sistemas de produção para efeito de projeto do sistema de produção			
b) Posicionar os processos de inovação e desenvolvimento de produtos dentro do projeto de sistemas de produção			
c) Discutir os conceitos básicos de inovação e desenvolvimento de produtos			
d) Discutir os conceitos de inovação de sustentação e inovação de ruptura			
e) Discutir conceitos do DNA do inovador			
f) Aplicar conceitos de projeto de inovação e desenvolvimento de produtos no contexto de um sistema de produção fictício			

Figure 1. Course syllabus

Figure 2 presents the contents of the Production System Innovation discipline from the first offer to the latter. In the first semester, the discipline focused on production system literature and innovation origins, especially concerning Schumpeter's discussion of creative destruction. A production system had to be analyzed, and the students had only one exam.

In the second semester, more content regarding innovation was inserted, including case studies of innovative companies, an activity to publish innovation news on a Facebook page, and a proposal to innovate in the previously analyzed production system. The same structure was replicated in the third semester. It provided more time exposure of students to the innovative concepts in practice. Starting in the fourth semester, the Professor suggested students start a business. Firstly, a business based on the Facebook platform, but since the fifth semester, a technology-based business. This proposal was compensated by getting off the syllabus the study of an existing production system. The Professor, intending to help students start a new business, added a more structured theoretical discussion regarding business model generation since the seventh semester. One of the exams was also removed from the syllabus.

Year	2012.2	2013.1	2013.2	2014.2	2015.1	2015.2	2016.1	2017.1	2017.2	2018.1	2018.2	2019.1	2019.2	2020.1
Production systems	Production systems	Production systems												Production systems
Innovation Origins	Innovation Origins	Innovation Origins	Innovation Origins	Innovation Origins	Innovation Origins	Innovation Origins	Innovation Origins	Innovation Origins						
Production System Analysis							Production System Analysis	Production System Analysis						
Innovation Deep analysis	Innovation Deep analysis	Innovation Deep analysis	Innovation Deep analysis	Innovation Deep analysis	Innovation Deep analysis	Innovation Deep analysis	Innovation Deep analysis	Innovation Deep analysis						
Innovation proposal							Innovation proposal	Innovation proposal						
One Exam	Two Exams	One Exam	One Exam					One Exam	One Exam					
Case	Case							Case						
Business models								Business models						
Documentary							Documentary	Documentary						

Figure 2. Content variation among ISP classes

From the eighth to the twelfth offer, more business model innovation theories were inserted. The Professor even eliminated the exams and inserted documentaries on new ventures, disruptive technologies, and past magnates of innovation to motivate students to propose good business models and work on the first conceptual prototypes. Almost 40 business models were generated, but only one startup was generated, with the students giving up fast. After reflecting on these results, the Professor found that a focus on business generation should be based on a deep study of existing production systems and good reasoning about how innovation can disrupt a production system.

These reflections impacted the change of the discipline syllabus in which the business model generation got off, and more theoretical content and exams were reinforced. This change is in course nowadays, and the statistical analysis here reported is part of this redefinition.

5.2 A review of students who concluded ISP

This section presents the results of the statistical analyses performed using the SAS® software. Based on the assessment records made between 1/2013 and 1/2020. Of the 219 initial records, seven students who had no assessment records (missing values) were unconsidered, i.e., they left the course, so they had no performance in the subject. In the evaluated period, the average grade of the students was 7.55 with a standard deviation of 1.59. It was also verified that the lowest score recorded was 1.01, and the highest was 9.90, indicating a large amplitude of scores, as shown in Figure 3, the boxplots of the students' final scores year of assessment.

From Figure 3, it is evident that the evaluation criteria adopted in the years 2017 and 2018 resulted in higher variation of grades among students. The period already mentioned where theory was decreased to focus on business model creation. On the other side, in 2016, the best grades among students were verified and the lowest variation of grades. This class has significant innovation activities, analyzing case studies in the classroom and the Facebook activities. It also had the only startup generated from the business models in the classroom.

Figure 3. Final scores of the students per year

A Multiple Linear Regression was performed from this initial exploratory analysis to identify the variables that present significant effects to explain the students' final grade (FG). From the whole set of ISP instances, 43 different evaluation forms were identified and submitted for regression analysis on the fourteen times it was offered. Whose the general linear model is presented in the following expression:

$$Y = X\beta + \varepsilon$$

where X is the matrix composed of binary variables relative to the evaluation mechanisms used in the period above, β is the vector of unknown parameters, and ε is the vector of unobservable model errors. The model assumptions were tested and validated.

Table 1 presents the results related to the Analysis of Variance, indicating that the adjusted model presents a coefficient of determination $R^2 = 0.9624$, which explains approximately 96% of the variation found in the dependent variable (FG).

Table 1. Analysis of Variance

Source of Variation	Degrees of Freedom	Sum of Squares	Average square	F	P-value
Model	8	12130	1516.30	653.08	<0.0001
Residues	204	473.64	2.32		
Total	212	12604			

The Stepwise method was used to fit the model. The selection of covariates that remained in the model was progressive, with the removal of covariates whose effects were not significant (p -value > 0.05). Table 2 presents the covariates that presented significant effects to explain the variation of the dependent variable (FG).

Table 2. Stepwise Method Fitted Model

Covariate	Estimated Parameter	Standard Error	F	P-value
Production System Analysis (X_1)	9.01823	0.71939	157.15	<0.0001
Group activities (X_3)	9.34561	0.47013	395.17	<0.0001
Economic evaluation of business models (X_{12})	-1.96667	0.42460	21.45	<0.0001
Prezi case study (X_{24})	8.12333	0.35915	511.59	<0.0001
Pirates of Silicon Valley movie (X_{34})	-17.79395	0.80562	487.85	<0.0001
One Exam (X_{35})	-1.40395	0.43110	10.61	0.001
Engagement evaluation (X_{36})	1.33252	0.67618	3.88	0.050
Final Presentation (X_{43})	7.60000	0.32486	547.31	<0.0001

The variables presented in Table 2 allow us to infer that production system analysis is a significant element in the final grades. Group activities and case studies have a significant impact. But the utilization of the movie Pirates of Silicon Valley negatively impacts final students' grades. Having Only one exam is not good for grades, neither is asking students to perform an economic evaluation of their business models. The final presentation and the analysis of students' engagement in the course also impact the final grades.

Based on the coefficients of the adjusted model. It is possible to verify the increase or decrease in the estimates of the final grades resulting from the covariates used as instruments for student assessment, as presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Estimates and Simulations of Final Scores given the Selected Evaluation Criteria

Covariates	X_1	X_3	X_{12}	X_{24}	X_{34}	X_{35}	X_{36}	X_{43}	FG	Error rate (%)
Year/Coefficients	9.02	9.35	-1.97	8.12	-17.79	-1.40	1.33	7.60		
2013_1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	8.1	6.0
2013_2	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	8.1	-10.4
2014_2	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	7.3	-0.3
2015_1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	7.6	-1.3
2015_2	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	7.5	0.4
2016_1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	7.9	-0.6
2017_1	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	7.4	-1.2
2017_2	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	7.4	0.9
2018_1	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	6.0	-0.3
2018_2	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	7.9	1.1
2019_1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	7.9	1.2
2019_2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	7.6	0.8
2020_1	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	7.6	0.1

According to Table 3. it is possible to see that the variables from the regression model can explain under a 2% error rate the average grades of every ISP class.

6 Final Considerations

Innovation is a theme to support new engineering courses. The new industrial revolution brings a more challenging environment for new engineers. This paper presented an innovation discipline whose variations on the content and evaluation method were gathered and compared.

We see those project-based learning elements, such as group activities, presentations, case studies, significantly impact the final grades. We also find that traditional methods impacted suggesting a necessary balance between engineering tradition and new engineering education methods.

Additional protocols could be applied to evaluate the discipline results for alumni, especially if they are working on the innovation subject if the course impacted this professional choice. A model for predict good students' results was generated, and new research protocols can apply it to new ISP classes for validation and analysis.

7 References

- Associação Brasileira Educação em Engenharia. (2018). Inovação Na Educação em Engenharia: Proposta de Diretrizes Curriculares Nacionais Para o Curso de Engenharia. Disponível: http://www.abenge.org.br/documentos/PropostaDCNABENGEMEI_CNI.pdf
- Balve, P., & Albert, M. (2015). Project-based learning in production engineering at the Heilbronn Learning Factory. *Procedia Cirp*. 32. 104-108.
- Barbalho, S. C. M., Reis, A. C. B., Bitencourt, J. A., Leão, M. C. L. D. A., & Silva, G. L. D. (2017). A Project-Based Learning approach for Production Planning and Control: analysis of 45 projects developed by students. *Production*. 27(SPE).
- Barbalho, S. C. M.; Rozenfeld, H. Modelo de referência para o processo de desenvolvimento de produtos mecatrônicos (MRM): validação e resultados de uso. *Gestão & Produção*. v. 20. pp. 162-179. 2013.
- Bell, S. (2010). Project-based learning for the 21st century: Skills for the future. *The clearing house*. 83(2). 39-43.
- Blumenfeld, P., Fishman, B. J., Krajcik, J., Marx, R. W., & Soloway, E. (2000). Creating usable innovations in systemic reform: Scaling up technology-embedded project-based science in urban schools. *Educational psychologist*. 35(3). 149-164.
- Borrego, M., Foster, M.J. and Froyd, J.E. Systematic Literature Reviews in Engineering Education and Other Developing Interdisciplinary Fields. *J. Eng. Educ.*. 103: 45-76. 2014.
- Caldeira, B. C., Morais, A. A., Mesquita, D. & Lima, R. M. (2017). Learning based on interdisciplinary projects with students from several engineering courses: case study on energy sustainability.
- Christensen, C. The innovator's dilemma: When new technologies cause great firms to fail. Boston: Harvard Business School. 1997.
- Clausing, D. (1994). Total Quality Development: a step-by-step guide to world-class concurrent engineering. The American Society of Mechanical Engineers. New York.
- Cooper, R. G. (2011). Winning at new products: Creating value through innovation. Basic Books.
- Downing, C. G. (2001). Essential non-technical skills for teaming. *Journal of Engineering Education*. 90(1). 113-117.
- Dyer, J., Christensen, C. M., & Gregersen, H. (2018). *DNA do Inovador: Dominando as 5 habilidades dos inovadores de ruptura* [tradução Esnider Pizzo e Mário Fernandes]. – São Paulo: HSM Editora. 2012
- Hmelo-Silver, C. E. (2004). Problem-based learning: What and how do students learn?. *Educational psychology review*. 16(3). 235-266.
- Koen, V., & Van den Noord, P. (2005). Fiscal gimmickry in Europe: One-off measures and creative accounting.
- Luz, K. S., Barbalho, S. C. M., & de Farias, M. C. O. (2021). Analysis of Learning Assessment Role Using Active Methodologies in "KAA" Perspective. 2nd South American IEOM Brazil Conference.
- Pugh, S. (1990). Total design: integrated methods for successful product engineering. Addison Wesley. London. The United Kingdom.
- Reis, A. C. B., Barbalho, S. C. M., de Araújo, F. L., Brito, L. S., Ishihara, S. E. M. P., & Teixeira, V. P. F. (2018). Project-Based learning: development of PBL-based competencies under the pupil's perspective. In *10th International Symposium Project Approaches in Engineering Education (PAEE)*.
- De Los Rios, I., Cazorla, A., Díaz-Puente, J. M., & Yagüe, J. L. (2010). Project-based learning in engineering higher education: two decades of teaching competencies in real environments. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*. 2(2). 1368-1378.
- Shumpeter, J. A. (1982). A Teoria do Desenvolvimento Econômico: uma investigação sobre lucros, capital, crédito e o ciclo econômico. *Coleção os economistas*. São Paulo: Abril Cultural.
- Wheelwright, S. C., & Clark, K. B. (1992). *Revolutionizing product development: quantum leaps in speed, efficiency, and quality*. Simon and Schuster.
- Yin, R. (2001). Estudo de caso: planejamento e métodos. Trad. Daniel Grassi. Rev. Cláudio Damascena. 2 ed. Porto Alegre: Bookman.
- Zindel, M. L., Mello da Silva, J., Souza, J. C. F., Monteiro, S. B. S., & Oliveira, E. C. (2012). A New Approach in Engineering Education: The Design-Centric Curriculum at the University of Brasília-Brazil. *International Journal of Basic & Applied Sciences IJBAS-IJENS*. 12 (5). 97 - 102. Retrieved from: http://www.ijens.org/Vol_12_I_05/127105-8585-IJBAS-IJENS.pdf